

dung). Survival again varied with cultivar (see table),

We found that mite eggs on Ratna grains were viable even after 6 yr in a refrigerator ($8 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), and could develop into adults on moist petri plates exposed to room temperature. We reared the mite in controlled conditions on media con-

taining different fungal diets. Mites multiplied vigorously on diets of *Alternaria padwickii*, *Fusarium moniliforme*, and *Curvularia* sp., but did not multiply on *Aspergillus flavus*, *A. niger*, and *Penicillium* spp. The life cycle of the mite is 6-7 d at room temperature ($26 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$).

Mites were found to migrate from

seeds to seedlings when seeds were sown in small pots. Percent grain germination of mite-infested grains was not adversely affected, but seedlings infested with a large mite population did not live more than 20 d after germination. Detailed studies on biology, bionomics, and etiology of this mite are in progress. □

Chemical control of the rice white leafhopper *Cofana spectra* (Distant)

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White leafhopper *Cofana (Tettigella) spectra* is considered a minor pest of rice, but is becoming more widespread each

year in Tamil Nadu. Nymphs and adults suck the sap from the leaf sheaths and leaves, which causes plants to become stunted and yellow. Severe infestations cause plant death.

We evaluated insecticides (see table) for white leafhopper control in the field using a randomized complete block design with four replications.

TNAU15776/3 was planted at 20- × 15-

cm spacing in 20-m² plots. Leafhopper populations for different treatments were recorded each week by counting insects on 20 randomly selected plants from each plot (see table).

Application of 1.25 kg ai carbofuran granules per hectare at 30 and 60 days after transplanting gave best control (see table). □

Effect of insecticide treatments on *C. spectra*, Coimbatore, India.

Treatment ^a	<i>C. spectra</i> population/20 hills ^b								
	58 DT	65 DT	72 DT	79 DT	86 DT	93 DT	100 DT	107 DT	Mean
Untreated check	9.8 c	9.5 d	13.3 d	12.3 d	10.5 c	11.5 c	10.5 c	10.5 d	18.6 e
Carbofuran granule at 1.25 kg ai/ha, 5 DT	7.0 a	5.8 ab	6.5 c	6.8 bc	6.3 b	4.3 a	4.3 ab	4.0 ab	5.5 c
Carbofuran granule at 1.25 kg ai/ha 30 DT, fb quinalphos spray 0.5 kg ai/ha 50 DT	9.3 bc	8.0 cd	5.8 bc	4.8 ab	5.8 b	4.8 ab	3.5 a	5.3 bc	5.8 cd
Carbofuran granule at 1.25 kg ai/ha 60 DT, fb monocrotophos spray 0.5 kg ai/ha 80 DT	6.8 a	6.3 bc	6.3 c	7.0 c	4.3 ab	4.3 a	5.3 ab	4.3 ab	5.5 ab
Carbofuran granule 1.25 kg ai/ha 5 and 30 DT, fb quinalphos spray 0.5 kg ai/ha 50 DT	7.0 a	6.3 bc	7.5 c	6.5 bc	6.3 b	6.5 b	5.8 b	6.8 c	6.5 d
Carbofuran granule 1.25 kg ai/ha 5 and 60 DT, fb monocrotophos spray 0.5 kg ai/ha 90 DT	8.0 bc	7.8 bcd	5.8 bc	6.0 bc	6.3 b	4.0 a	4.0 ab	3.5 ab	5.6 c
Carbofuran granule 1.25 kg ai/ha 30 and 60 DT	7.3 ab	5.3 a	3.0 a	3.8 a	2.5 a	3.0 a	3.3 a	2.5 a	3.8 a
Carbofuran granule at 1.25 kg ai/ha, fb quinalphos spray 0.5 kg ai/ha 50 DT and monocrotophos spray 0.5 kg ai/ha 80 DT	6.0 a	6.0 bc	4.0 ab	4.5 ab	4.3 ab	4.5 ab	4.8 ab	3.3 ab	4.6 b

^a fb = followed by, DT = days after transplanting. ^b In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

Rice thrips outbreak in the Visweswarayya Canal (VC) tract

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Late rains delayed the release of irrigation water from the Krishnaraja Sagar reservoir catchment area in 1983 and

drought and dry weather apparently favored the fast multiplication of rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) during the wet season. Thrips severely damaged high yielding rice cultivars planted in the VC tract in Sep.

In a hill, 60 to 70% of the leaves were infested and up to 22 nymphs and 5 adults (av 5 and 1.5) per leaf were record-

ed. Infestation was most severe 10 to 15 d after transplanting and lasted as long as 40 to 45 d.

Application of carbofuran 3G at 0.5 kg ai/ha or foliar application of monocrotophos 40 EC or phosphamidon 100 EC at 0.05% gave good control. After a moderate rainfall during the infestation, the thrips population was reduced. □